

Humanistic Approach and Teaching of Science

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Abstract

Humanistic approach to education implicates factor of humanity and context in education. Science may comprise of logic and facts but cannot be value free. It is imperative in present scenario to include not only to contextual aspect of science in the teaching material but also make it student centric in nature. This paper focuses on the evolution of humanistic approach of science education and also the responsibilities and application of this approach in teaching of science. There are various schools of thoughts for humanist approach and it can be used to inculcate sense of morality and can be used as a catalyst for transformation of one's reality. This paper also talks about how we can humanize our approach towards teaching of science by understanding the historical perspective of science, making the class room interaction more humane, and discuss socio-scientific issues in the present times.

Key words: Humanistic Approach, Science Education, Contextual Learning and Dialogue |

Introduction

In current times, we see a major shift of interest of students from science to other streams in search of better career avenues. This lack of interest also can be attributed to poor classroom practices, rote learning and a gap in the classroom transaction of knowledge and real life situation. However, it is more pertinent than ever to instill in the students an interest towards science and scientific method. The complex tribulations faced by the society as large for example, global warming, climate change and ongoing pandemic can be resolved only if we face it as scientifically literate and aware citizens. It is vital for our curriculum to include social and contextual aspects in the curriculum so that students in their formative age can see the subject not just as a mumbo jumbo of facts and figures but also empathize with humanist side of science and apply it in real life.

Science curriculum needs to be reorganized around "contextual settings and science stories" which will help the student to appreciate the fact that science as a subject is entrenched with "scientific and humanist traditions" (Stinner, 1995).

Even fields like engineering and technology which are considered 'hard sciences' based on cold, logical facts and replete with disciplinary rigor cannot be isolated from the humanistic aspect. Engineers are not just designing building and machines in a closed room; they are harbingers of major social changes with their work. The industrial revolution which happened centuries before and created mighty civilizations, was a result of an engineering feat. (Hynes & Swenson, 2013)

With advent of new technology like telecommunication and internet world has become a global village. With this globalization no nation can function in isolation whether in terms of economical aspect or culturally. Economic recession in one nation can have a domino effect all over the world and it will have an effect on the political and social equation. (dos Santos & Mortimer, 2002)

Science in school setting should equip the students to "know science", "do science" and also learn "about science", this means that they must possess content, process and contextual skills. (Bryce, 2010)

Learning about science or the nature of science prepares the students to develop skills like decision making, critical thinking and logical reasoning. Collaborative and interdisciplinary nature of science when explored can facilitate the spirit of inquiry and understanding of multiple perspectives. Humanistic science education will not only aid the major population of students who need meaningful science education assisting them in making informed decisions in real life scientific dilemmas for example, Genetic modified food, garbage disposal etc. but also instill passion for science in those who aspire to make a career in science.

The fundamental property of humanistic education is to “accept and believe in human existence” and to work towards to make a difference in the humanity.

The Historical Context

The idea of science as we know today is a western construct, with European and American influences. Prior to the evolution of western sciences, region specific indigenous sciences and knowledge were in practice in different regions like India, South East Asia and Africa. With the advent of agriculture the populace was segregated into givers and takers. This led to the development of the formal subject of science, where the entity involved in the menial job of tilling the land was not involved in generation of scientific knowledge but the philosopher or thinker pondered on the questions of science. There was a gap between the theoretical and practical aspect of science where scientific knowledge was limited to laws and theories propounded by experts and knowledge. Doing experiments and gathering experimental data was considered a menial job hence was shunned by the academia. This changed during the industrial revolution where concept of science were applied for economic growth

There always been an interaction between culture and technology, the development of technology affects our social cultural and political realities. Technology improves the quality of life, it also poses threat to humanity as seen in various technology induced disasters for example Bhopal gas tragedy and Chernobyl nuclear leak aftereffects of which are still seen in the newborns. (dos Santos & Mortimer, 2002)

Humanistic Science Teaching

The process of science teaching has always aimed to prepare students for a career in science and engineering. The funneling of students with high intellect into science and engineering degrees is also known as “pipeline Phenomenon”. The students whose career goals are not a part of this pipeline are uncomfortable with the notion of science which is taught in schools. An alternative approach to teaching of science is to view the subject in context of society and culture. This is known as the humanistic approach. It aims to develop the students’ capacity as responsible, savvy participants in their everyday lives increasingly affected by science and technology.

There is a definite need of major changes in the way we teach science in our classrooms. The traditional pedagogy of science has had a lot of shortcomings. We see a major decline in students taking up science as an option for higher studies as the current method relies a lot on rote learning and dry facts without any practical knowledge and application and the students tend to lose interest and not develop an affinity towards the subject in order to pursue it as a career option. Another drawback of teaching science in a traditional format is that the students fail to “learn science meaningfully”. The ability to apply and integrate the scientific knowledge gained in a classroom in real life would help make a responsible citizen who does not fall prey to superstitions and various fake narratives peddled so easily in this age of social media. (Aikenhead, 2004)

There are different approaches to humanist science education. In any humanist approach primal importance is given to the “human” Factor and this human factor can be interpreted in several ways. It could be by imbuing moral values in the students whilst imparting scientific knowledge, it can also mean contextual aspect of the subject where science is taught in a way that is more relevant to students

life.(Hadzigeorgiou, 2012) There are different approaches to humanist science education for example STS (science, technology and society) based education and SSI (socio-scientific issues) based instruction. The various humanistic approaches to science education were listed by Hadzigeorgiou in his monograph, which are as follows

a) Liberal Education b) Progressive Education c) Critical Education d) transformative education e) Humanistic/ Therapeutic Education and f) Existentialist Education.(Hadzigeorgiou, 2005)

All these approaches have a common facet of having contextual setting in the subject rather than having a value free and apolitical stance towards it.

There has to be a personal or a social connect with course matter to make it humanist. A personal issue could be the benefits of eating organic food and how eating pesticide free fruits and vegetables can be a healthier option. It is an issue which has its root in science and yet affects all of us in present times. There can also be social issue like frequent pandemics and natural calamities which affect the society as a whole and the reasons behind it.

Rutherford gave three criteria for a course to make a course humanistic

- 1) It should have sufficient connection to liberal or humanistic sciences.
- 2) It should be humane in which the way it is taught in class.
- 3) It must have a focus on 'humanistic factor' in the subject.(New, 1946) There is minimal progress in inculcating humanist values in teaching of science and there can be a plethora of reasons for that; disinterest at the level of policymakers, logistical problems of administration in schools but the two major reasons behind this shortcoming can be:
 - a) The teaching staff at the very basic level not understanding the term and implications of humanistic science teaching.
 - b) There is no proper framework or a model which enables the teachers to teach the subject on the lines.

Science Teaching and Humanities

"Science is an enterprise socially constructed, communicated and validated" (Stinner, 1995)

Evolution of science as a subject has always been affected social, cultural and political issues of the time. It is not dependent on the logical and formal determinants only so it is important to study the history of science in order to humanize science.(Wang & Marsh, 2002) For example in U.S.A. post the launch of Sputnik, a renewed disciplinary rigor was introduced in the science curriculum in order to equip the students with complex scientific concepts and create a generation of students who can later become scientists and engineers. This was a direct result of the ongoing space war between U.S.A and U.S.S.R.

These instances show the dynamic nature of science and how, a scientist as a member of society interacts with the society and the government and this interaction affects the evolution of science. By demonstrating the perpetual change in the nature of science which is not just an aberration but a rule, students of science can be shown how the society affects science and how we can always question present beliefs and create new scientific knowledge.

An interesting example of amalgamating history in science is the chapter of "Structure of Atom" at secondary level science. The chapter scales the entire timeline leading to the present model and theory about structure of atom. This demonstrates the transient and tentative nature of science but also opens up possibilities of future research for students. It also helps the students to understand how scientific knowledge is created with logical steps and valid arguments. History of science not only develops the critical thinking of the students but also improves the conceptual understanding of the concept.

Incorporating the historical aspect of science also assists in developing Procedural understanding of the subject. The process of designing of an experiment to prove a theory helps give an insight about the **Scientific Method** involved in generation of knowledge. Understanding scientific method is essential for a responsible citizen as scientific method is not only limited to the creation of scientific

knowledge, but it is beneficial in making informed and responsible decisions in daily life as well. The practice of teaching only the “final product” in a traditional classroom can be detrimental for the understanding of nature of science.

Historical perspective in science also gives an idea about the **Contextual Basis** of the scientific knowledge. Though the scientific laws may be universal but there are sociopolitical and cultural aspects factoring in generation of knowledge. The Second World War era had some of the most momentous discoveries in such tumultuous times because of the race amongst Allied and Axis powers to surpass each other in terms of weaponry and technology. As the saying goes that the “necessity is mother of invention”, the outcomes of that chaotic and volatile era are some of the most path breaking inventions. Another way we humanize the science education is by educating the students about the struggles and triumphs of the scientists who beat all odds to achieve greatness and contribute towards the world of science. The achievements of female scientists like Madame Curie and Lady Ada Lovelace can provide role models to the young students in their formative age.

There is always a gap or division between the science and arts to make the pure science to look more daunting than it is, but “neither great scientists nor artists agree with it”. (Hadzigeorgiou, 2012)

Frierean Perspective of Humanistic Science Education

Paulo Freire has been one of the most significant educational thinkers of all times. His work pedagogy of oppressed has influenced various fields like education, journalism, political science and theatre etc. The term ‘Critical Pedagogy’ signifies that of education which is value free or without context is a sign of oppression. The idea of education is to acquire critical thinking and awareness of the social climate around the student. Friere’s idea of humanist education was to bring change in the society. It went “beyond teaching content without social meaning and bringing about a change”. (Dos Santos, 2009)

According to Friere, it is imperative for the oppressed to understand the context of the knowledge transacted and how it affects the society. Education is meant to bring change in the conditions of the oppressed and for them to be able to comprehend their role and responsibilities in the current social and political climate.

For a country like India where we see a huge social and economical chasm between the people, humanist approach to science can be a way to educate about the social disparity in terms of the consumption of science and technology, where the oppressive elite is reaping economic benefits by ravaging the environment and the oppressed has to suffer the consequences of the excesses of elite. The rampant deforestation for urbanization and industrialization is not only disturbing the ecological balance but also displacing the indigenous tribes and destroying the livelihood. The poor and oppressed bear the brunt of the climate change and natural calamities caused by the oppressive elite. According to Freire, to create ‘collective consciousnesses about the injustices faced by the oppressed, they need to have education which not only informs but also empowers them to transform their reality.

Another significant principle of Frierean pedagogy is ‘**Dialogue**’, a dialectic process between student and teacher is essential so that a student is not considered as an inanimate object and an empty vessel to fill. It upholds the idea of a democratic classroom where there is a back and forth between the two important components of a class. “It through dialogue men and women are humanized” and it has the ability to change our reality. (dos Santos & Mortimer, 2002)

Inclusive Science Teaching: “Humaneness in Science Teaching”

Any “curriculum of scientific knowledge is inherently humane by nature” as it makes us distinctly aware of the world and its workings and puts us apart from other creatures of the world. (Donnelly, 2004) In a classroom setting, day to day teaching is influenced by the affective aspect of teaching. The enthusiasm and emotion of the teacher towards the subjects is rubbed off to the students. (Bryce, 2010) A very important prerequisite of a humanist approach is having a democratic classroom where the students are considered equals and their views are valued.

If there is a disparity between how a male and female or low scoring and high scoring student is treated in the class, there is bound to be loss of passion for the subject. (New, 1946) Inclusive science education essentially would not discriminate on the basis of gender and also purity of language of the student. If any student is admonished for not learning the exact definition of an abstract law even though understanding its implication it hampers the natural curiosity and joy of learning science. It is necessary to modify the method of evaluation in the subject to become more collaborative and application based. This also holds true for differently abled students where there has to be a sense of positive discrimination for such students where the ultimate aim is not equality but equity amongst the students.

Criticism of Humanist Approach

One of the major criticisms of humanist approach is that it will compromise on the quality of scientific knowledge and narrow down or “deemphasize the science teaching”. The purity of scientific concepts can be in danger of watered down by introducing the human aspect in it. But counter that opinion it can be said that just because science till now was taught in a “sterile, authoritarian and dogmatic approach” (Hadzigeorgiou, 2012) doesn’t mean it was been taught effectively. To make science more approachable and meaningful for all students it is necessary to explore this approach of science teaching. However this raises the question that by altering the traditional science teaching to make it science for all we may deprive the prospective scientist and science educators, the students who possess true passion for the subject, recognize the aesthetics of logical science facts and wish to make a career in it. That is also an important goal of teaching science

Another issue with humanist way is to devise an optimum curriculum which maintains the sanctity of science but also is contextual and student centric at practical level. It still requires research, deliberation and discourse amongst all the stake holders i.e. the teachers, policymakers and administration. The teachers also need to be equipped with skills to make the classroom a democratic and humanist without compromising on the quality of scientific knowledge.

Conclusion and Implications

To make a classroom humanistic there has to be a change in which not only how a scientific course is taught but also how it is designed. There is a dilemma while designing a scientific course whether it should be aimed to create a select few future scientists or a course suited for all which caters to all and seeks functional scientific literacy. It is necessary to create a balance between both aims of education where there is a ‘human factor’ in science and still manages to create an interest in the content and preserves disciplinary rigor of the subject. (dos Santos & Mortimer, 2002)

In a classroom the teacher has to create a sense of wonderment in the student with inherent aesthetics of science and give a context to the concept from student's own reality so that a student can imbibe it in a better way. For example a student interested in sports will understand the laws of motion in a better way if it is set in a cricket or football setting. (Hadzigeorgiou, 2005)

There is minimal progress in inculcating humanist values in teaching of science and there can be a plethora of reasons for that; disinterest at the level of policymakers, logistical problems of administration in schools but the two major reasons behind this shortcoming can be:

- a) The teaching staff at the very basic level not understanding the term and implications of humanistic science teaching.
- b) There is no proper framework or a model which enables the teachers to teach the subject on the lines.

There is the daunting task of developing a curriculum which caters to all kind of students, whether they want to make a career in science or not, a course structure which ties up the conceptual, contextual and personal aspects of the subject. The students need to possess not only scientific knowledge but also science process skills and critical thinking for betterment of society. A lot more research and discourse

is needed to come with a feasible solution to all these problems. It is imperative to do this to achieve the goal of universal scientific literacy and a better society and environment.

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